

Preparation and Characterisation of Barium Hydroxylapatite with Arsenate

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Calcium hydroxylapatite $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, (CaHA) is the principal inorganic constituent of bones and teeth¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions². $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Ba}^{2+}$ and $\text{PO}_4^{3-} \rightarrow \text{AsO}_4^{3-}$ exchanges result in the formation of a series of solid solutions of hydroxylapatite containing arsenate,

Earlier methods of preparation of solid solutions of BaHA with arsenate by the solid state reaction³ were however found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous. Now an attempt has been made at a new method of preparation of the homogeneous solid solutions over the entire compositional range by the method of coprecipitation⁴.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of the samples are given in Table 1. Observed values of molar g-atomic ratio Ba/P and Ba/As for end-members and Ba/(P + As) for the intermediate were found to be equal to 1.665 (theoretical 1.67) which is consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solutions⁵. This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end-members and those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members.

The formation of solid solutions can be confirmed further by the X-ray diffraction analysis. It is well established that all the members of the apatite series exhibit hexagonal crystals, belonging to the hexagonal bipyramidal class 6/m (space group $\text{C6}_{3/m}$)⁶. Lattice parameters showed unit cell dilation consequent upon the introduction of larger ion AsO_4^{3-} ion (2.48 Å) in the apatite lattice.

This of course, is the real evidence for solid solution in this series and clearly shows that these preparations are not mixtures of two components or one component with adsorbed material.

Experimental

Samples were prepared by precipitation in CO_2 -free atmosphere at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ by simultaneous dropwise addition of stoichiometric quantities of barium nitrate solution (A) and solution (B) containing AsO_4^{3-} and PO_4^{3-} ions in the proportion desired for solid solutions. All solutions were prepared separately in CO_2 -free double-distilled water. Both solutions were maintained basic ($\text{pH} > 11$) during the precipitation reaction and subsequent digestion. To a part of solution (A), solutions (A) and (B) were added dropwise simultaneously. Precipitation was carried out in CO_2 -free atmosphere to prevent the formation of carbonate apatite. The precipitate and mother liquor were aged by boiling under reflux for 1.5 h to improve the homogeneity and crystallinity of the precipitate. The maintenance of the desired pH during precipitation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate, since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of cation deficient apatites⁷. The precipitate was allowed to settle overnight, and washed repeatedly with double-distilled water till the washing was neutral. It was then filtered, dried (110°) and analysed complexometrically⁵. The molar volumes were determined by density method using toluene⁸ as a solvent.

After drying at 110° and then heating at 950° for 5 h the samples were subjected to X-ray diffraction study on a Siemens powder diffractometer with NaCl(TL) counter employing CuK_α (nickel filtered) radiation with a scanning speed of 1 degree 2θ per min using tube voltage of 30 kV and 24 mA.

TABLE 1 – CHEMICAL ANALYSIS, LATTICE PARAMETERS AND UNIT CELL VOLUMES OF BARIUM HYDROXYLAPATITES AND ITS SOLID SOLUTIONS WITH ARSENATE

Sample no	Weight %			Molecular formulae	Molar volume	Gram-atom ratio Ba/P+As	Lattice parameter (Å)		Unit Cell volumes (Å) $\sqrt{3}/2 a^2 c$
	Ba	P	As				a	c	
1	69.454	9.406	—	Ba ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	369.65	1.664	10.19	7.70	692.42
2	68.000	7.736	3.56	Ba ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{5.04} (AsO ₄) _{0.96} (OH) ₂	372.43	1.666	10.25	7.82	711.51
3	66.614	6.136	6.976	Ba ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{4.08} (AsO ₄) _{1.92} (OH) ₂	372.55	1.665	10.33	7.94	733.75
4	65.251	4.565	10.322	Ba ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{3.10} (AsO ₄) _{2.90} (OH) ₂	368.98	1.666	10.41	8.04	754.55
5	63.852	2.954	13.578	Ba ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{2.05} (AsO ₄) _{3.95} (OH) ₂	375.12	1.665	10.50	8.13	776.25
6	62.537	1.439	16.989	Ba ₁₀ (PO ₄) _{1.02} (AsO ₄) _{4.98} (OH) ₂	372.20	1.666	10.62	8.23	803.86
7	61.287	—	20.059	Ba ₁₀ (AsO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	370.52	1.664	10.68	8.35	824.82

Barium hydroxylapatite and its solid solutions with arsenate are hexagonal with two lattice constants a_0 and c_0 . These were determined for all samples by measuring the diffraction angle (2θ) of the three planes, (312), (213) and (321). Each sample was thoroughly mixed with 25 % NaCl (recrystallised from HCl) which served as a standard so that the observed values of $\sin\theta$ for the solid solution lines could be directly corrected for absorption and instrumental errors. The lattice constant of NaCl at 26° was taken to be 5.6403 Å⁹. A least-squares calculation on the corrected values of $\sin\theta$ for the three reflection, then gave the two parameters a and c for each sample. The average probable error in unit cell parameters is less than ± 0.003 Å.

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